

Feedback at Scale

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Abstract

This paper explores effective feedback design in the context of large class cohorts in higher education. In recent years, there has been a significant shift in emphasis with regard to feedback, moving from a focus on inputs to processes. Large classes in higher education pose particular challenges to all aspects of assessment processes, including feedback. The complexities of enabling effective feedback processes are examined leading to suggestions to enable students to obtain and use good quality information about their work. While the active role of the student is central to the current discourse on feedback processes, the role of teacher is also important, moving from providing comments on work to designing processes that work effectively for learning.

Keywords: *feedback; large classes; student engagement; assessment; higher education.*

1. Introduction

It has been established for a long time that feedback for students is one of the most powerful influences on learning (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Shute, 2008). The past decade has seen a revolution in research about feedback and although its influence is just as important as ever, we now think differently about how we do it and what constitutes doing feedback well (Boud & Molloy, 2013; Winstone and Carless, 2020). There has been a shift of focus from what teachers and supervisors do in providing comments, to what learners do in terms of engaging with the feedback process (Henderson et al., 2019).

However, at the same time, the landscape of higher education has been characterised by unprecedented growth. Teaching large classes is presented as an access or social justice issue, placing a moral burden on higher education teachers to teach in these complex contexts, increasing workload and changing the nature of their work (Allais, 2014). This paper explores the tensions between enabling feedback to maximise learning and the complex landscape of the large class teaching and learning environment. It complements the keynote presentation for the PHELC26 online symposium.

2. Enacting Effective Feedback

The past decade has seen a major conceptual shift in the discourse relating to feedback in higher education, moving away from a *teacher*-centric to a *learning*-centric perspective, whereby the emphasis is not on inputs but rather on processes and what students do (Boud and Molloy, 2013). Traditional approaches to feedback are problematic because students receive information they may not know what to do with, too late to apply it or the justification of a mark substitutes for guidance. To be effective, feedback must signpost the future direction of a student's learning journey. It also requires students to play an active role throughout the feedback process; rather than passively receiving unsolicited comments; they need to actively seek and make sense of feedback information to improve their future work. This has implications for the role of the teacher, the design of assessment across a programme and the development of students' feedback literacy skills. The emphases above illustrate a move away from the onus on the teacher (noun) to provide isolated pockets of information, to focus on

learning (verb) impact, shifting the focus from the person to the action, and from one person (the teacher) to the actions of another (the student).

In this context, feedback serves a range of purposes for learners such as enhancement of learning, providing new perspectives, identifying next learning steps, tailoring learning to individual needs, and monitoring progress; all of which ultimately should lead to developing the capacity of students to evaluate the quality of their own work and that of others (Tai et al., 2018). Therefore, provision of feedback information needs to be disentangled from grading/marking (Winstone & Boud, 2022) as feedback which justifies a grade is essentially backward-facing only, usually commenting on work students have completed and does not meet most of the purposes previously identified. Feedback must also occur when students are in a position to act on it, before they have to tackle a subsequent task, rather than at the end of a unit which is not linked to other future units of learning. This implies purposeful feedback design at programme level as well as unit/module level. Provision of feedback is one of the few ways in which a course can be tailored to individual student needs and interests; however, addressing that individuality has to be designed into a programme rather than left as the responsibility of individual teachers. Enabling holistic feedback design demands feedback literacy skills on the part of both teachers and students. Teachers need to understand how to move from being mere information-providers to facilitators who design feedback-rich environments to enable students to develop their own evaluative judgement and expertise in a field.

The ‘feedback loop’ is a learning-centric process that is only considered complete when the learner takes specific action to improve their performance, creating a cycle of continuous improvement. The feedback loop contains four key components:

1. **Initiation and elicitation** - For feedback to be effective, the learner is the initiator. Students need to be enabled to elicit information from others and communicate the specific kinds of information they find useful for their work. This places them in an active role rather than a passive one as merely a recipient.
2. **Feedback inputs** - The learner then receives ‘inputs’ (feedback/information) about their work which can emanate from a range of sources e.g. teacher, peers, non-human sources.

3. **Sense-making and processing** - The learner then must make sense of the information received and use it to enhance their future work and/or learning strategies.
4. **Closing the loop** - The most vital part of the process is enactment. Feedback has not occurred unless the learner completes the loop by using the information to work on and enhance their learning performance. Successful feedback is evident in what students subsequently do.

For the feedback process to occur as outlined above, a programme needs to be designed so that these cycles are visible in a sequence of tasks and occur when a student is still in a position to act. This has serious implications for course and programme design. Assessment and feedback are two pillars of pedagogy, along with teaching, learning and curriculum; pedagogy also concerns relationships and values and ‘is fundamentally concerned with what people perceive to be meaningful, important and relevant as they engage in teaching-related activity’ (Nind et al., 2016, p.9). Course design necessitates consideration of all pillars of pedagogy, including feedback, from the outset to reduce fragmentation and make visible the learning trajectory for participants. Moreover, feedback is a two-way process, which should inform teaching as well as student learning; in this way, effectively designing feedback systems within a carefully considered pedagogical design should inform teacher learning and development also.

3. Considering Feedback in the Large Class Context

Definition of what constitutes ‘large’ in terms of class size in higher education, seems be related as much to perception as to quantification (Mantai & Huber, 2021; Maringe & Sing, 2014), although there seems to be some tentative agreement that ‘large class’ relates to those cohorts of 100+ students (Exeter et al., 2010). However, regardless of perception or quantification, the impact on pedagogy in this context seems evident, often focusing on the limitations presented including increased workload (Allais, 2014); reduced teacher-student interaction and overuse of a ‘talk-at-them’ approach (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010); inflexible physical environment which limits opportunity for student-student engagement (Nicholl & Lou, 2012); and, teaching which is aimed at an ill-defined middle, whereby

students experiencing difficulty go unnoticed because teachers cannot judge how individuals are performing (Arvanitakis, 2014).

Assessment at scale can be perceived as onerous (Foley & Masingila, 2014) with the assumption that options are limited (Kerr, 2011). At a basic level, logistics and management of assessment at scale can appear overwhelming with the sheer volume of assignments to be marked making it difficult to manage and meet university deadlines and that continuous assessment is not possible (De Matos-Ala & Hornsby, 2015). There can be reliance on sessional staff to engage with the marking process which leads to difficulties with standardisation, consistency and maintenance of quality when many people are involved in evaluation of student work (Broadbent et al., 2018).

Given the complexity of learning in a large class context, the feedback principles discussed earlier take on greater importance than may be the case with small class cohorts. However, enacting the principles of an effective feedback process are challenging because of the practical constraints inherent in the large class context.

The volume of assessment generated by a large group may make it difficult to provide detailed feedback (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010) in a timely manner (Exeter et al., 2010). In particular, individualising feedback of any quality can seem impossible (Broadbent et al., 2018), and teachers may also perceive that any feedback that is provided is not acted upon and/or ignored by students. However, these problems can be overcome. To do so requires a workload allocation system that allocates staffing resources commensurate with priorities for learning. That is, pivotal courses, such as those required in first year should not receive reduced staffing to allow for small classes in later years.

Feedback does not always require student-teacher interaction; in large cohorts, such interaction is limited (Maringe & Sing, 2014) and therefore needs to be supplemented with other strategies that enable students to get good quality information about their work. It may appear that in the large class context, it can be difficult to gauge overall class understanding and impossible to ascertain individual student understanding of key concepts and therefore identify individual students who may be struggling (Voelkel & Bennett, 2014). However, this is a design problem which can be addressed through the use of sessional staff, non-human resources such as self-testing systems and use of peers. Examples of these

approaches even in classes of over 1,000 students can be found in the rich case studies presented at <https://feedbackforlearning.org/>

4. A Solution-Focused Framework for Effective Feedback Design for Large Class Cohorts

The word ‘perception’ appears in much of the literature around large class pedagogy, specifically in relation to what can and cannot be done in that context, with the context itself ill-defined and in the eye of the beholder. The teacher’s ability to recognise the benefits of the large class is an enabler for the identification of opportunities for collaboration, interaction and active learning in that context (Mantai & Huber, 2021). This section outlines some illustrations of enabling feedback processes specifically in the complex environment of the large class. What follows emphasises the importance of designed feedback processes, positioning both students and teachers as generators and receivers of feedback.

4.1. The Importance of Design of Feedback Processes

There are many strategies for enabling feedback at scale; however, these are reduced to tips and tricks without overall programme level design. The following design frameworks outline some possibilities for large class cohorts:

- (a) *Programmatic assessment*, sometimes referred to as programme focused assessment, in its purest form, moves beyond the development of isolated, high-stakes assignments and examinations toward a longitudinal architecture wherein individual data points are aggregated to provide a robust, triangulated view of a learner’s competence. In this framework, programmatic learning outcomes are central and assignment tasks should be aligned with these as well as with module learning outcomes (van der Vleuten et al., 2012). Professional learning opportunities are in-built to enhance the skills of those designing assessment, while students are viewed as agentic partners in the process (Baartman et al., 2023; Heeneman et al., 2022). Planned, ongoing, iterative feedback is fundamental to programmatic assessment design, with the expectation that students enact feedback as they progress through the programme (Torre & Schuwirth, 2025). For very large programmes, the management of

assessment data, monitoring progress over time and ensuring consistency among programme staff is challenging. Yet, it is exactly these large cohorts which need this design the most as they navigate the complexity of learning new, disciplinary concepts alongside hundreds of peers.

- (b) *Iterative and linked assessment design* connects assessment tasks to allow for a level of coherence across a course and builds in explicit opportunities for students to use feedback information from one assignment for the next. In the large class context, this may have to be enacted within a year rather than across years depending on numbers of students and indeed, staff. Depending on the nature of the design, the workload for staff working on a large programme may be more streamlined, with quality of feedback prioritised over quantity.
- (c) *Building student feedback literacy* enables students to take greater responsibility for their own feedback processes (Carless & Boud 2018, Molloy et al., 2020). If students are to have a greater role in feedback, they need to develop the competencies needed to do so. Teachers have a vital role in building their capacity to do this and it is becoming an important feature in large first year classes. Activities are structured not only to help students with the substantive subject matter, but simultaneously build their feedback literacy (Malecka et al., 2022). There is a burgeoning literature on how feedback literacy can be built into courses (Little et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2026) and simple open access tools for judging students' feedback literacy have been developed (Dawson et al., 2024).

All of the above have implications for tracking engagement and monitoring progress over time which is challenging to accomplish at scale.

Whatever approach to design is adopted, specific feedback strategies need to be enacted. The following section provides some suggestions to strategies which might be enacted with large cohorts.

4.2. Peer Feedback

In large classes, peer feedback can be a powerful tool. However, as with all pedagogical aspects in this context, it needs to be carefully considered and structured. It can be used both in-class and in take away activities.

- *Think-Pair-Share* type activities in-class explicitly enable students to share, discuss and engage with ideas and concepts with each other. Small tasks may be created to allow students the opportunity to examine key concepts and ideas.
- *Technology* can be used to enable peer-to-peer engagement on a more formal basis. For example, tools such as PeerWise™ have been shown to be particularly useful for large groups (Kay et al., 2020). It can be used in-class and between classes to enable students to pose questions, respond to the questions of others and to provide feedback on responses received (Farrell, 2021). It also allows students to evaluate quality in terms of judging the usefulness of a question to aid learning as well as the quality of responses to their own question and those of others. Depending on the needs of the group peers can be anonymous to each other but not to the teacher, which allows for mediation to correct learner misconception and extend learning.
- *In-class polling* allows students to demonstrate their understanding. It is a safe way to respond to questions in a large class context. Platforms such as Vevox™ and Kahoot™ enable teachers to assess learning in real time. While the peer-to-peer feedback is more limited than is the case in the previous two suggestions, polling does allow students to get a sense of the overall understanding of their peers in relation to their own conceptual development. In the large class, where students are often reluctant to contribute in front of peers (Auslander, 2000) in case they are ‘wrong’, in-class polling allows the student voice to be captured. Indeed, in the large class context, this type of student engagement is more powerful than with smaller cohorts precisely because of scale.
- *Oral contributions* - following on from the point above, developing a culture of contribution in a large class context simultaneously enables whole-class discussion and peer engagement. However, in most cases, this will not happen organically; rather, it needs to be explicitly scaffolded (e.g. Farrell, 2022). Recruiting some students at the beginning of a unit and providing them with questions to ask and/or responses to questions posed

to the whole class means that students, in partnership with the teacher, model two-way engagement, discussion and feedback leading to normalisation of this dialogic relationship.

Peer feedback can also be used for tasks outside the lecture. Having students make comments on the assignments of peers is becoming increasingly common and it benefits both the recipient and well as the person providing comments. Peer feedback activities need to be well structured and students reassured that discussions about their work does not constitute collusion, as they might fear. Guidance from the research literature on peers providing feedback information is now available (Little et al., 2025) and examples given of how it might be used in combination with other activities (Hoo et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2026). However, care must be taken to position this as feedback and not as peer assessment (Sridharan et al., 2019) as the latter can create conflict and ethical dilemmas.

The strategies above speak to student agency and enable opportunities for them to learn from each other. While not the focus of this paper, it is worth highlighting that enabling in-class peer feedback and engagement contributes to the creation of a classroom community; an aspect of the teaching and learning experience that is often overlooked or assumed to be automatically impossible to garner with very large class cohorts.

5. Concluding Thoughts

Although contemporary thinking about feedback processes puts emphasis on the active role of students, the role of the teacher becomes more important than ever. However, it shifts from one of providing comments to students on their work to one of designing courses that work effectively for feedback. This is crucial in large classes as it is no longer possible for teachers to do all the feedback-giving work themselves, even if it were desirable to do so. An important part of this is creating feedback-rich environments in which students can gain insights into their own work from a variety of human and non-human sources, and to build students' own feedback processing capacities through developing their own feedback literacy. The latter requires teachers themselves to extend their feedback literacy beyond that of designing tasks and giving comments to feedback design especially for large

classes (Boud & Dawson 2023). Again, resources to enable educators to judge their own teacher feedback literacy are now available (Istencioglu et al., 2026).

Of course, the greatest challenge to considerations of feedback, especially in large classes is the rise in use of Generative Artificial Intelligence. The widespread availability of genAI means that any student at any time of the day or night can receive comments on their work from a chatbot whether or not this is allowed by the policy of the institution in which they are enrolled. The implications of this are profound and much research is underway to explore implications for feedback practices. It would be premature to discuss the implications of this for feedback at scale, but while it is clear that they will be profound, it is too early to say how we should best navigate our way through it as it confronts us with wicked problems that we should approach with caution and with no expectation of clean solutions (Corbin et al., 2025).

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